

Measuring Emotions in Product Design: A study on Emotional Responses to Car Designs

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Abstract

People interact with different objects and environments during their life-time; feeling and expressing emotions toward the surrounding objects. Emotions have become one of the most progressive topics of industrial design discipline in recent years, especially with human factors studies, raising the need for investigating the area of emotions in product design. Desmet (2002) defines the emotions that are expressed towards a product as ‘product emotions’. In the present study, PrEmo (Product Emotion Measurement Instrument) developed by Desmet (2002) was used. The aim was to investigate emotional responses to a specific product group, to determine differences across gender groups and to apply an emotion measurement instrument in Turkey to see its validity and usability in a different context. More specifically, the study aims to answer the following research questions: What are the emotional responses of the participants towards the given products? Do the participants from different gender groups differ in terms of their emotional responses to each product given in the instrument? Is PrEmo a suitable and usable measurement instrument in the context of Turkey? Finally, key concepts of emotional design, mainly developed by Desmet (2004, 2003, 2002), were reviewed. The paper reports an empirical research utilizing self-report methodology to assess emotional responses to photographs of seven concept cars in the Turkish context and shows how different product characteristics were perceived differently by men and women.

Conference Theme: Measuring Emotions

Keywords: Emotion Measurement, PrEmo, Turkish context, Gender Differences

Emotional Design

User-centered design and different genders' approach are receiving more attention in design in recent years. An ergonomic or user-friendly design is attracting more attention than a high-tech design, and manufacturers are now investing in human-factors, emphasizing a user-centered design policy in their marketing campaigns. Jordan (2000) states that the aim of human factors is to add value to products in order to make them usable. However, he also adds that usability alone is not enough for a 'satisfying' product. Identifying the needs of customers should be considered not only in technological terms, but also in aesthetical and emotional sense.

As Jordan (2000) says, people are always in the search for satisfaction. To specify the 'wants' of people, he developed a 'hierarchy of consumer needs', using Maslow's model of "hierarchy of needs" (1970). Basically, this model has three steps, functionality, usability and pleasure. According to the theory, once people reach a lower level of satisfaction, they start to desire the next upper level of satisfaction. Jordan (2000) points that more pleasure-based products should be designed, as 'usability' alone is not enough anymore as a product attribute and users demand more from products. They want added-value such as emotional properties. However, identifying user needs in terms of emotional satisfaction can be difficult, as emotional data seems intangible and subjective. As Desmet, Overbeeke and Tax (2001) mentioned, emotions are specific for each person. It may be difficult to explain why one product is loved by a user and hated by another. Desmet and Hekkert (2002) define the relationship between product and emotion with a model called "Basic Model of Product Emotions" which has four elements describing the process of an emotion: (1) appraisal, (2), concern, (3) product, and (4) emotion (Figure 1). In this model appraisal is the way how the user perceives the product. A pleasant emotion is aroused by the user, when the product is perceived beneficial. If a product is appraise as beneficial, this means it matches the user's concerns.

Figure 1: Basic model of Product Emotions (Desmet, 2002)

People experience various types of emotions during their life-time. Furthermore, these emotions are classified in different ways by researchers. The types of product emotions are examined to determine which types of emotions are evoked by products. Well-known studies about product emotion classifications are from Jordan (1998) and Desmet (2002).

Jordan (1998) conducted research to determine pleasurable and displeasurable feelings in relation to products and the connection of product properties with feelings. In his study, each participant was asked to think about one pleasurable and one displeasurable product they owned or used. Then an interview was held with each participant and they were asked about their pleasurable and displeasurable feelings about these two products. As a result of this study Jordan proposes that pleasurable feelings towards products are security, confidence, pride, excitement, entertainment, freedom, and nostalgia; and displeasurable feelings are aggression, feeling cheated, resignation, frustration, contempt, anxiety, and annoyance.

Desmet (2002) distinguish emotions from each other according to their similarities and contrasts which he names as ‘underlying dimensions of emotions’ (p. 11). He uses a two dimensional diagram with x dimension of pleasantness (from unpleasant to pleasant) and y dimension of activation level (from high activation to low activation) to describe the variations of emotions. This two dimensional diagram was created by Russell (1980) and named “The Circumplex of Emotions” (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The Circumplex of Emotions (Desmet, 2002)

To uncover the set of emotions generated by product appearance (product relevant emotions) to be represented in each octant in the Circumplex, Desmet (2002) conducted a series of studies, as the existing emotion sets were not representing every emotion relevant to products.

Figure 3: The Circumplex of 41 Product Relevant Emotions (Desmet, 2002).

Finally, a set of 41 product relevant emotions representing emotions aroused by products was determined (Figure 3).

Product Emotion Measurement

Finding accurate and appropriate consumer data is a challenge for designers. Various techniques have been developed to communicate the user data. Desmet (2002) mentions that today there is a range of methods and tools, from various types of high technology computer measurement techniques which can make sensitive physical measurements to simple low-tech surveys where participants are asked to express themselves with pen and paper. However, the most considerable methods involve the use of product emotion measurement instruments that focus on the evaluation of emotional expressions, physiological reactions and subjective feelings concerning products.

Measuring emotion has been used as a method in the fields of psychology and sociology. Following the increasing importance of the role of emotion in product design, marketing researchers started to use different emotion measurement methods to capture consumer

emotional data, mostly by computer-based techniques. However, Desmet (2003) states that none of the existing emotion measurement methods are capable of measuring product emotions and responses towards products. He believes that one needs to characterize and classify emotions before building a measurement method. Desmet (2003) categorizes the self-reporting emotion measurement instruments in two groups according to their dependence on speech; as: (1) Non-verbal measurement instruments, (2) Verbal measurement instruments

The instruments that measure non-verbal expressions can be used in multi-cultural contexts. Although verbal instruments can measure mixed emotions, they have some limitations such that they are not appropriate to be used between cultures; and many people can not verbalize their momentary emotions easily or truly.

Product Emotion Measurement Instrument (PrEmo)

Desmet (2002) developed an emotion measurement instrument, specifically designed for measuring product emotions: Product Emotion Measurement Instrument (PrEmo). PrEmo is a non-verbal self-reporting instrument. The aim of developing this new instrument was to combine the advantages of non-verbal and verbal measurement instruments (Desmet 2002). The advantages of PrEmo are that it can be used in different cultures, as it is a non-verbal measurement instrument; and it can measure mixed emotions rather than basic ones, as the participant are able to give a scale for each emotion. Norman (2003) finds Desmet's instrument practical and clever, as compared to the existing ones. The main idea of PrEmo is the universality of emotional expressions (facial and bodily) across cultures. PrEmo uses cartoon animations to describe 14 distinct emotions: seven pleasant emotions (i.e. desire, pleasant surprise, inspiration, amusement, admiration, satisfaction, fascination) and seven unpleasant emotions (i.e. indignation, contempt, disgust, unpleasant surprise, dissatisfaction, disappointment, and boredom).

However, a limitation of the instrument is that it cannot be reliable in interactive human-product relation, as it is designed for the emotions evoked by the product appearance. Moreover, Norman (2003) further states that none of the measuring instruments can solve the problems of meeting behavioural and emotional needs that come from demographic variations.

To examine the validity of PrEmo's animations, Desmet (2003) conducted a research with participants from four different countries: Japan, United States, the Netherlands, and Finland. As a result, except *desire* and *disappointment* the tool was validated. These two emotions were re-

examined and re-developed as it was invalid in Japanese context. After validation process, he applied PrEmo in a multi-cultural context with 68 participants from the Netherlands and Japan. He used car models as stimuli, as car models evoke strong emotions in appearance (Desmet, Hekkert and Jacobs, 2000). The participants were shown 6 car models in random order with PrEmo. To determine the differences between cultures, Desmet applied a two-way repeated measure, MANOVA, for each emotion. Desmet (2003) reports the results as: in three emotions (admiration, satisfaction and fascination) Japanese participants did show higher mean scores, meaning that they showed more admiration, were more satisfied and fascinated by the car models than Dutch people.

Methodology of the Study

For the present study, a pilot study was done prior to the main research. The pilot study was conducted with six similar family sedan car models (see Appendix A), with similar colour and price ranges. Consequently, respondents reported that the car models looked too similar when they were viewed in PrEmo. Thus, the participants got confused and found it difficult to rate the cars. Moreover, the pilot study showed that the differences in emotional responses for such similar cars were not significant among the participants.

Subsequently, the decision was made to use different styles and categories of cars for the main research (see Appendix B). The aim was to identify consumer emotions towards the selected products and the gender differences. Research assistants (N= 60) at the Faculty of Architecture, Istanbul Technical University participated in this study in 2007. The study was applied to 30 male and 30 female research assistants aged between 23 and 42. The participants were selected in order to apply the study to a homogenous group in terms of their educational background, age and monthly income. Photos of seven car models were used as stimuli and were shown in random order with PrEmo.

Data were analysed using SPSS 11.5 version. Following the descriptive analysis of the results, and to explore the effect of gender on the emotional responses, the analysis of the data was made for each of the 14 measured emotions with MANOVA. MANOVA was run seven times for each car model with gender (two levels) as between-participant factor, and the emotions (14 levels) as dependent variable.

Findings of the Study

In the descriptive analysis phase, the votes of the participants for each car were examined to comprehend which emotion was felt towards which product. Figure 3 shows the means of 14 emotional responses to all seven cars.

Figure 4: Means of 14 emotional responses to the seven cars

In figure 4, it can be seen that Car A (Bugatti Veyron) evoked positive emotions among participants. The most elicited emotion was *admiration* and the least elicited one was *boredom*. Next, participants expressed more negative emotions towards Car B (Hummer H3); where *dissatisfaction* was the most elicited emotion, and *amusement* was the least elicited one. Car C (Kia Ceed) was the car model which evoked more positive emotions among participants, mostly *fascination* and *satisfaction*. Participants did not express much *indignation* and *disgust* to Car C. Similar to Car C, Car D (Peugeot 908 RC) evoked *admiration* and *fascination* more frequently. The emotions *indignation* and *disgust* were the least experienced ones. Car E (Pininfarina Nido), Car F (Renault Koleos) and Car G (VW Iroc) were the other car models that evoked mostly

positive emotions. The most elicited emotion overall was *fascination* and the least elicited emotion was *unpleasant surprise* to Car E, Car F and Car G.

Participants expressed more negative emotions to Car B and more positive emotions to Car D. However, Turkish people did not understand the animation representing *amusement*. It was perceived as a negative emotion among participants rather than a positive one which is a difference in cultural perception.

Following the descriptive analysis, the effect of gender on the emotional responses has been explored and the differences between male and female participants' responses on seven car models analysed. Figure 5 provides the plot of the means across gender and emotions towards the seven cars.

Car C

Car D

Emotions

Car E

Emotions

Car F

Emotions

Car G

Figure 5: Plot of the means for gender groups on expressed emotions to seven cars

According to the MANOVA results, significant difference was found between genders on the *amusement* emotion for Car A and Car F, meaning that male participants felt more *amusement* than female participants towards Car A and Car F. However, the descriptive analysis showed that the *amusement* emotion was misinterpreted by Turkish participants. Consequently, this variable should not be interpreted as a significant difference.

For Car B the significantly different emotion among genders was *boredom*. Male participants found Car B more boring than female participants. No significant difference was found between gender groups on the emotions expressed towards Car C and Car D. Car E was the car model that had the most significant difference between genders on the emotions related to *desire*, *admiration* and *satisfaction* which means that female participants expressed significantly more positive emotions towards Car E. Towards Car G, significant difference between genders was found for the emotion of *contempt*. This can be interpreted as male participants feeling more contempt than female participants towards Car G.

Discussion and Conclusion

There are several reasons for using PrEmo in this study. The main reason is because it is a non-verbal measurement instrument that also uses self-reporting technique. A non-verbal research method can be used in a multi-cultural context, as participants do not hesitate to express themselves in a non-verbal method, and as translating emotions in a verbal way can be difficult.

Participants reported that the software interface is easy and enjoyable to use, as there are animation characters that portray dynamic facial, bodily, and vocal expressions of each emotion. However, participants held the questionnaire seven times to vote for each car one by one. Thus, some of the participants reported that it took too much time and effort to complete the task. The participants also reported that the emotional expressions of the animated characters are similar, especially for the positive emotions. Participants added that they could hardly find a difference between the various positive emotions. Moreover, the animation portraying *amusement* was perceived as a negative emotion by Turkish participants. Participants thought that the animation for *amusement* is like a short laugh of persiflage.

Although PrEmo has several benefits, it also has limitations. It measures the emotions expressed towards static representations of product design, as Desmet (2003) also mentioned, it does not measure emotions that are experienced towards dynamic human product interaction. In addition,

and as mentioned previously, participants pointed out that to evaluate each product individually and selecting among each 14 emotions for each one of them takes a lot of effort and time.

The present study also has several limitations. It was conducted on a group of research assistants from Istanbul Technical University, Faculty of Architecture, and the results are only generalizable to that limited population. The study needs to be replicated with different population samples in order to ensure the consistency of the findings. Another limitation of the study is that the surveys are only valid for the time they are implemented. Replication at a different time with the same population is also needed.

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Appendix A

The car images used in the pilot study

VW Polo

Citroen C3

Fiat Punto

Ford Fiesta

Honda Jazz

Hyundai Getz

Toyota Yaris

Appendix B

The car images used in the research

Car A Bugatti Veyron

Car B Hummer H3

Car C Kia Ceed

Car D Peugeot 908 RC

Car E Pininfarina Nido

Car F Renault Koleos

Car G VW Iroc